

CONTEMPORARY METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN JOURNALISM EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this thesis, examines modern methods of teaching English lexis to students learning it as a foreign language. It highlights the importance of vocabulary over grammar in developing communicative competence and analyzes the role of terminology, idioms, and lexical phrases in effective language learning. The research also emphasizes the integration of digital tools and Internet resources to enhance vocabulary acquisition and learner motivation. The author concludes that applying modern linguodidactic principles and innovative approaches can significantly improve the efficiency and quality of English language teaching in higher education.

Keywords: lexis, methodology, communicative competence, terminology, idioms, lexical approach, Internet technologies, English as a foreign language

Introduction

As a result of the extensive reforms currently being implemented in the field of education, a modern national system based on international qualification standards has been developed to improve the quality of education, including the professional competence of foreign language teachers. Among these reforms are the efforts to

incorporate communicative competence-based approaches into the learning process, which aim to enhance the scientific and pedagogical quality of foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan.

The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-1875 dated December 10, 2012, “On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages,” established foreign language learning as an integral part of the primary education process. The decree set out to increase interest in learning foreign languages, raise the general level of education, and promote intercultural cooperation. Hence, one of our primary tasks today is to develop a modern methodology for teaching foreign languages based on international practices (Presidential Decree, 2012).

Result and Discussion

English has become one of the leading languages in global communication. In science, technology, culture, education, and business, proficiency in English is one of the essential requirements of the modern world. Not every concept or phenomenon can be expressed by a single word, which often necessitates the creation of new compound lexical units or terms. Learners spend a significant amount of time studying vocabulary and prefer to use dictionaries containing frequently occurring words. However, dictionaries alone do not teach language use, as they do not provide information about context or communicative function. Therefore, language learning should not only focus on isolated lexical elements but also on their usage and contextual features (Halliday, 1978). This research aims to explore effective methods of teaching lexis and terminology, and to demonstrate their importance in the language learning process.

Review of Literature

A number of scholars have investigated methods for teaching foreign languages within the Commonwealth of Independent States, including O.V. Koryakovtseva, N.V. Titarenko, and A.V. Zhukova. Studies focusing on teaching foreign language

vocabulary were conducted by M. Choriev, M. Djusupov, M. Nazarova, N. Babaniyazova, S. Nazarova, and Sh. Butaev. Western scholars such as Halliday (1978), Widdowson (1989), Wills (1993), Sinclair (1991), Nattinger and DeCarrico (1992), McCarthy (1990), Carter (1987), and Hunston and Francis (1998) have examined the qualitative improvement of vocabulary instruction. In higher education, the development of linguistic and cultural competence among future specialists has also been studied by Uzbek scholars such as Sh. Sharipov, O. Musurmonova, Sh. Mardonov, S. Nishonova, D. Ruzieva, B. Khodjaev, D. Sharipova, N. Egamberdieva, M. Quronov, A. Nurmanov, and S. Tursunov.

Object of the Study and the Used Methods

The research focuses on students in higher education institutions who study English as a foreign language, particularly journalism students learning media-related English terminology.

The study employs several methods, including the analysis of theoretical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis of translation methods, surveys, and testing.

Teachers should always keep in mind that learning a language essentially means learning meanings. According to Halliday (1978), language is a product of social interaction and arises during communication. Effective vocabulary teaching enables learners to use learned words in meaningful contexts. Linguists emphasize that developing true communicative competence in English depends more on teaching lexis than grammar. Lewis (1993) asserts that language is not grammar-based lexis but rather grammar that conforms to lexis. Similarly, Widdowson (1989) notes that communicative competence relies not on the knowledge of rules but on accumulated linguistic experience and skills. However, emphasizing lexis over grammar does not mean excluding grammar from instruction. On the contrary, both are interrelated. Wills (1993) argues that grammar and lexis represent two ways of

expressing the same linguistic purpose: words convey meaning, and grammar provides structure. Thus, grammar and vocabulary should be taught simultaneously.

Terminology, derived from the Latin ‘terminus’ and Greek ‘logos’, refers to the science of terms. Reformatsky (1986) defines the primary function of a term as the naming of objects and phenomena, typically expressed as nouns. Doniyorov (1977) also concludes that only nominal terms qualify as terminology objects. Therefore, it is essential that students understand the formation and linguistic characteristics of professional terms, as terminology constitutes an integral part of the lexical system. Abdullaeva (2015) suggests two approaches to introducing new terminology: with and without translation. The choice depends on various factors such as the term’s features, its active or passive use, students’ proficiency level, and the context of introduction (classroom, textbook, or dictionary).

Sinclair (1991) identifies two principles governing natural language use—the ‘open choice principle’ and the ‘idiom principle’—and states that idiomatic usage predominates in authentic communication. Nattinger and DeCarrico (1992) highlight the advantages of learning lexical phrases, including increased fluency, easier memorization, and more effective communication. McCarthy (1990) and Carter (1987) define idioms as restricted combinations whose meanings cannot be inferred literally, such as ‘to let the cat out of the bag’. Hunston and Francis (1998) further emphasize the grammatical correlation between lexical and syntactic patterns.

Teaching Methods

Since the number of lexical items in a language is virtually infinite, teachers must adopt efficient and context-based strategies for vocabulary instruction. Activities that promote self-directed learning and awareness-raising should be prioritised. Teachers should also consider learners’ needs and goals when selecting vocabulary to enhance motivation and practical usage. The following methodological principles are key to vocabulary and phraseology instruction: (1)

lexical-grammatical correlation; (2) systemic approach considering lexical paradigms; (3) contextual analysis; and (4) lexical-syntactic connection. These principles help students comprehend the meaning and usage of words and phraseological units within context.

The Role of the Internet and Social Networks

Integrating Internet resources into English classes provides numerous didactic advantages, including increasing students' cognitive engagement, encouraging active participation, and offering access to authentic and up-to-date materials. It enables learners to interact with speakers from other cultures and to apply their language knowledge in real-life situations (Arora, 2022). Moreover, online platforms facilitate the learning of vocabulary, idioms, and terms relevant to students' professional domains, such as journalism.

Conclusion

In conclusion, incorporating modern linguodidactic achievements into the process of teaching English vocabulary and terminology, and applying innovative methods based on both local and international perspectives, significantly enhances the quality and effectiveness of instruction. Teachers should select vocabulary based on learners' professional needs and interests, develop their understanding of phraseological principles, and utilize Internet resources for practice. Teaching English terminology, especially in specialized fields such as journalism, should take into account students' linguistic background in both English and Uzbek.

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JURNALISTIKA TA'LIMIDA INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisda ingliz tilini xorijiy til sifatida o'rganayotgan talabalarga leksikani o'qitishning zamonaviy usullari yoritilgan. Muallif grammatikaga nisbatan leksikaning kommunikativ kompetentsiyani shakllantirishdagi ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi hamda terminlar, idiomalar va leksik

birikmalarning til o'rganishdagi o'rnini tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, leksikani samarali o'rgatishda raqamli vositalar va internet manbalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati ko'rsatilgan. Muallif zamonaviy lingvodidaktik printsiplar va innovatsion yondashuvlarni qo'llash orqali ingliz tili ta'limi samaradorligini oshirish mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksika, metodika, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, terminologiya, idiomalar, leksik yondashuv, internet texnologiyalari, xorijiy til sifatida ingliz tili

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ЖУРНАЛИСТСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация. В данном тезисе освещены современные методы обучения лексике для студентов, изучающих английский язык как иностранный. Подчеркивается важность лексики по сравнению с грамматикой в формировании коммуникативной компетенции, а также анализируется роль терминов, идиом и лексических фраз в эффективном обучении языку. Особое внимание уделяется использованию цифровых инструментов и интернет-ресурсов для повышения мотивации и усвоения словарного запаса. Автор приходит к выводу, что применение современных лингводидактических принципов и инновационных подходов значительно повышает эффективность и качество преподавания английского языка в вузах.

Ключевые слова: лексика, методика, коммуникативная компетенция, терминология, идиомы, лексический подход, интернет-технологии, английский как иностранный